

Contents

Contents	1
Scenarios as presented in the survey	2
1. The Autonomous Car.....	2
Version 1.0.....	2
2. AI Based Recruitment System.....	2
Version 1.0.....	2
3. Chatbot in Customer Service.....	2
Version 1.0.....	3
4. AI System Monitoring Elderly People in their Homes.....	3
Version 1.0.....	3
5. Deep Fake Finishes a Movie.....	3
Version 1.0.....	4
Explanations of the qualitative codes	5
Breakdown of qualitative codes, per scenario	7
Validation of the qualitative analysis	8

Scenarios as presented in the survey

1. The Autonomous Car

The family Johnson is riding through the city in an autonomous car, to visit a restaurant. There are both autonomous cars and human-driven cars among the traffic. None of the passengers are steering the vehicle, it is controlled by an AI system. The autonomous car only uses the same traffic information a human driver would work with in the traffic, via sensors, and the autopilot has been trained with data from human decision-making while driving. What could go wrong?

Version 1.0

The family Johnson is riding through the city in an autonomous car, to visit a restaurant. There are both autonomous cars and manually steered cars among the traffic. None of the passengers are steering the vehicle, it is controlled by an AI system. Due to the hybrid environment, the autonomous car only uses the same information a human driver would work with in the traffic, via sensors, and the autopilot has been trained with data from human decisions in driving. What could happen?

2. AI Based Recruitment System

A company uses an AI-based tool to choose new employees to join its ranks. The AI system sorts out the applicants based on their CVs and cover letters to suit the company's agenda. After the AI has chosen the best applicants based on the initial applicant information, the applicants are given a questionnaire to fill, where the choices they make reveal information about their personalities. The AI system analyzes the questionnaire results based on the company's historical preferences and invites the most suitable ones into an interview that is finally conducted by a human. What could go wrong?

Version 1.0

A company uses an AI-based tool to choose new employees to join its ranks. The AI system sorts out the applicants based on their CVs and cover letters to suit the company's agenda. After the AI has chosen the best applicants based on the initial applicant information, the applicants are given a questionnaire to fill, where the choices they make reveal information about their personalities. The AI system analyzes the questionnaire results based on the company's historical preferences and invites the most suitable ones into an interview, that is finally conducted by a human. What could happen?

3. Chatbot in Customer Service

Anna, who is quite inexperienced with using the newest technology, is browsing an online pharmacy website, looking for an over-the-counter treatment for a common but rather intimate problem. She normally does her shopping at the local pharmacy, but due to social distancing, she decided to shop online for the first time. She has trouble choosing the right product. She sees that there is a chat available that promises to enable her to talk to a

pharmacist to ask for advice with her problems. The chat opens with a chatbot instead of connecting to a real person, but the announcement of connecting to a chatbot instead of a real person is implemented in a long wall of text. Anna's sight is slightly impaired, which makes it hard for her to concentrate on the text. What could go wrong?

Version 1.0

Anna, a 68-year old woman is browsing an online pharmacy website, looking for an over-the-counter treatment for a common but rather intimate problem. She has trouble choosing the right product. She sees that there is a chat available that promises to enable her to talk to a pharmacist to ask for advice with her problems. The description of the chat does not clearly state that the chat opens with a chatbot instead of connecting to a real person. What could happen?

4. AI System Monitoring Elderly People in their Homes

An AI based monitoring system is installed in the home of an elderly man who suffers from Alzheimer's and has less ability to live independently. He is very reluctant to go to a caretaking facility, and the health care personnel state that he can live by himself on the condition that a family member is responsible for monitoring him. The family wants an outsourced 24/7 monitoring. With the written consent of the man, they install an AI system designed to monitor elderly people and analyze their behavior based on both the data of the individual and the entire pool of behavioral features the system has gathered. Based on this data, the system can send status updates and alarms to the family based on the elderly man's actions. What could go wrong?

Version 1.0

An AI based surveillance system is installed in the home of an elderly man who suffers from Alzheimer's and has a lowered ability to live by himself. He is very reluctant to go to a caretaking facility, and the health care personnel deem him just about fit enough to live by himself, on the condition that a family member is responsible for monitoring him and checking up on him daily. The family wants 24/7 surveillance and, with written consent of the man, installs an AI system designed to monitor elderly people and analyze their behavior based on both the data of the individual and the entire pool of behavioral features the system has gathered.

5. Deep Fake Finishes a Movie

The crew has almost finished filming a new action-filled treasure hunter movie. The movie has an abundant budget, but it is speculated to be a big hit and bring in earnings that match the investment. The narrative includes a plot for an intimate romantic relationship between the protagonist, Anthony, and his old rival, Isabel, who turn from enemies to lovers as the story progresses. In the latter part of the production, the actress of Isabel gets into a car accident and ends up in a coma. The director is anxious to finish the movie despite the absence of the actress due to the high stakes in the production. The unfinished end of the movie is also where the romantic story arc gets the most screen time. The director makes the decision to use technology that has never been used in a big budget production before:

since they have enough data from the already filmed material, they utilize an AI-based system (Deep Fake Technology) to produce a fake likeness of Isabel on screen. The artificially created version of the actress imitates her body language, voice and expressions to the point that it is impossible for audiences to tell the fake Isabel from the real one. The movie is finished and published before the actress wakes up from her coma. What could go wrong?

Version 1.0

The cast of a movie has almost finished filming a new action-filled treasure hunter piece that's speculated to be a big hit. The narrative includes a romantic side plot between the protagonist, Anthony, and his old rival, Isabel, who turn from enemies to lovers as the story progresses. In the latter part of the production, the actress of Isabel gets into a car accident and ends up in a coma. The director is anxious to finish the movie despite the absence of the actress, and she has a solution. The director makes a decision to use the technology that has never been used in a big budget production before: they use an AI system to produce a fake likeness of Isabel on screen, since they have enough data from the already filmed material to train a Deep Fake . The artificially created version of the actress imitates her body language, voice and expressions to the point that it is impossible for audiences to tell the fake Isabel from the real one. The movie is finished and published before the actress wakes up from her coma. What could happen?

Explanations of the qualitative codes

Code markdown	Code full name	Explanation
accessibility	accessibility	the system is impossible or more difficult to use for certain people with restrictions or disabilities, or they are at an unfair disadvantage while using the system
agency	agency & supervision	over-reliance on the system by the people using it or abandonment of active supervision due to blind trust in its judgement
FA priorities	ethical priorities	the system has priorities that do not align with human moral code or quality requirements
FA inaccuracy	inaccuracy	the system does not consider all the relevant details and nuances
FA incompetence	incompetence	the system does not achieve the desired effect
FA adaptability	lack of adaptability	the system does not adapt to changing circumstances or support progress
FA potential	missed potential	the system doesn't meet the highest potential
PP	physical problem	A problem caused by the physical surroundings/environment, or other devices the AI works in cooperation with
privacy	privacy	an individual's privacy is compromised either by data leak risks, or in the psychological sense
exploitability	system exploitability	the system is vulnerable to deliberate exploitation by a malevolent party or usage with bad intentions
other technical	technical or physical problem	non-AI related technical problem
TDL	training data limitation	The system is limited or has a likelihood of performing badly due to the limited data it has been trained on
transparency	transparency	issue caused by lack of transparency in how the system works / the system is not easily understandable in the situation
accountability	unclear accountability	it is unclear who is accountable/responsible in case of harm
UTHQ	unfavorable transfer of human qualities	the system is likely to perform badly due to a transfer of incompetent or biased human decision-making into the algorithm
bias	bias & unfairness	the AI is likely to make decisions that are biased or discriminate against a group of people, or the system inherently promotes inequality

financial harm	financial harm	risk of financial loss for individuals
human rights	human rights	a human's ability to govern themselves or control their own life is compromised. Includes consent issues (and a person's diminished chances of interacting with the system due to personal limitations)
legal issues	legal issues	the system causes legally dubious situations or legal problems to someone involved
NBE	negative business effects	negative outcomes for a business entity
physical harm	physical harm	physical harm to individual
psych harm	psychological harm	psychological harm to the individual
social harm	social harm	an individual's standing in society or relation to other people is negatively affected. Includes also people developing traits that make it more difficult to navigate society, such as developing a fear or dislike to technology
USE	unwanted societal effects	negative effects at the level of society or societal systems such as healthcare, or the system contributes to negative phenomena on a societal level

Breakdown of qualitative codes, per scenario

Code name	Total	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5
accessibility	6	0	0	6	0	0
accountability	9	4	0	2	2	1
adaptability	29	10	13	0	5	0
agency	14	2	4	3	5	0
bias	36	7	23	4	2	0
exploitability	9	1	5	1	1	1
financial harm	7	1	1	1	0	4
human rights	39	1	1	9	15	13
inaccuracy	39	2	6	12	19	0
incompetence	19	5	2	9	2	1
legal issues	17	0	0	2	2	13
negative business effects	23	0	13	6	0	4
physical harm	47	22	0	13	12	0
physical problem	4	3	0	1	0	0
potential	6	6	0	0	0	0
priorities	14	5	8	1	0	0
privacy	34	0	5	13	14	2
psychological harm	30	0	0	15	6	9
social harm	21	0	1	1	8	12
training data limitation	41	14	10	3	4	0
transparency	20	1	2	15	2	0
unfavorable transfer of human qualities	26	14	11	0	1	0
unwanted societal effects	28	3	1	1	10	13

Validation of the qualitative analysis

This section contains the validation of the qualitative analysis results made by an external researcher.

The validation analysis was performed on randomly selected response units.

In the table, **O** = original analyst, **E** = external analyst, who performed the validation analysis. The rows of O and E depict the analysis results written by the two analysts. The markdown made by the analysts may include shortened versions of the names of the qualitative codes, listed earlier in 'Explanations of the qualitative codes'.

The **similarity points** -row presents the similarity score of the analyses. 1 point was granted for every *non-matching code* (including the lack of one). Therefore, *the lower the score, the higher the similarity*.

O1	UTHQ physical harm FA unethical	UTHQ TDL FA potential	PP TDL FA adaptability agency UTHQ	FA incompetenc e TDL	FA incompetenc e TDL	PP physical harm
E1	UTHQ transparency physical harm FA priorities FA adaptability	UTHQ TDL FA adaptability FA potential physical harm	PP TDL physical harm agency UTHQ	TDL physical harm FA priorities	FA potential FA incompetenc e	PP FA potential FA incompetenc e physical harm FA inaccuracy
Similarity points	4	2	2	3	2	3
O2	bias FA priorities FA adaptability	UTHQ bias privacy	bias FA adaptability UTHQ TDL	NBE bias	TDL FA adaptability exploitability	TDL
E2	bias transparency TDL USE	bias TDL unfairness privacy legal issues	bias TDL FA adaptability unfairness UTHQ	bias financial harm	TDL financial harm exploitability	TDL
Similarity points	5	4	2	1	2	0

O3	FA incompetence FA inaccuracy privacy	physical harm FA incompetence	human rights transparency privacy FA incompetence physical harm NBE FA unethical	physical harm FA incompetence privacy	FA incompetence human rights transparency privacy	accessibility human rights
E3	FA potential FA incompetence privacy transparency	FA incompetence physical harm	transparency privacy FA incompetence agency FA adaptability FA priorities human rights physical harm	FA incompetence physical harm TDL privacy	TDL FA inaccuracy privacy FA incompetence psych harm	accessibility agency
Similarity points	3	0	5	1	5	2
O4	privacy FA inaccuracy USE physical harm	human rights legal issues	human rights privacy PP agency social harm FA inaccuracy	USE PP FA inaccuracy physical harm	human rights privacy TDL FA inaccuracy	TDL FA inaccuracy FA adaptability
E4	exploitability FA incompetence physical harm transparency	privacy legal issues	transparency privacy PP agency physical harm social harm TDL	FA incompetence physical harm	privacy human rights TDL physical harm	TDL AI incompetence
Similarity points	7	2	4	4	2	3
O5	human rights psych harm USE legal issues	legal issues social harm financial harm USE	privacy human rights system exploitability social harm financial harm	human rights psych harm USE privacy		social harm legal issues psych harm

E5	human rights USE financial harm legal issues	legal issues financial harm social harm USE	privacy financial harm social harm	human rights legal issues social harm		social harm legal issues
Similarity points	2	0	2	5		1